
A CORPUS OF ANCIENT EGYPTIAN EMBALMING PLATES

Francisco Luis Borrego Gallardo
(Universidad Autónoma de Madrid)

ABSTRACT

The ‘embalming plate’ is a type of artefact that is mentioned quite frequently in the literature on ancient Egyptian mortuary practices. However, it has not been well studied so far. This paper is a preliminary corpus that can serve as a basis for further studies of this kind of objects, as an open list that can be expanded in the future. This corpus is divided into four lists: A) pieces removed from the mummies with which they were associated; B) doubtful examples; C) items discovered by the x-raying or scanning of mummies; D) embalming plates currently in two display cases in Room 22 at the Egyptian Museum in Cairo.

KEYWORDS

Ancient Egyptian mortuary practices, mummification, embalming plate, amulets, wedjat-eye.

RESUMEN

Las placas de evisceración constituyen un artefacto mencionado recurrentemente en la literatura sobre las prácticas funerarias del antiguo Egipto que, sin embargo, no ha sido estudiado en detalle. Este artículo se presenta como un sencillo corpus preliminar que sirva de base para ulteriores estudios de esta clase de objetos, como una lista abierta que puede ser ampliada en el futuro. El corpus está dividido en cuatro listas: A) piezas retiradas de las momias con las que estuvieron asociadas; B) ejemplares dudosos; C) ítems descubiertos con radiografía o escaneo de momias; D) placas de evisceración actualmente en dos vitrinas de la sala 22 del Museo Egipcio de El Cairo.

PALABRAS CLAVE

Prácticas funerarias del Egipto antiguo, momificación, placa de evisceración, amuletos, ojo udyat.

The so-called ‘embalming plate’, ‘embalmer’s plaque’ or ‘incision-plate’ is a type of artefact documented between the New Kingdom and the Late Period that is mentioned quite frequently in the literature on ancient Egyptian mortuary practices¹. However, it has not been well studied so far. Thus, detailed descriptions, complete publications and overall analyses on them are quite rare.

Besides some royal examples of the Third Intermediate Period, most of the known examples of embalming plates are those found with the mummies of the priests and priestesses of Amun of the Twenty-first and Twenty-second Dynasties who were buried in the collective tomb of Bab el-Gasus (Deir el-Bahari, Western Thebes)². However, this corpus is also the worst known and published. The descriptions of the G. Daressy, the Egyptologist in charge of reporting the objects found with the mummies, very meagre and without figures or photographs³, are the only first-hand source for their understanding. Some of these pieces are apparently on display at the Egyptian Museum in Cairo (Room

¹ Smith 1912: 105; Smith and Dawson 1924: 152-153; Goff 1979: 114 and 147; Taylor 1995: 60; 2001: 55; Ikram and Dodson 1998: 128; Janot 2000: 4, 56-57, 151 and 154.

² Sousa 2018, with earlier references.

³ Daressy 1902; 1903; 1908.

22). During a visit to this museum in August 2019, I had the opportunity to take several photographs of the two display cases where this type of artefact is exhibited. Next to each piece a number was written on a black card, which is most likely the number given to them in the Special Register (SR 8715-8738 and 8758-8771)⁴. In this work, I have decided to include a brief description of these pieces. Although there may be redundancies concerning the items coming from Bab el-Gasus, I think that this is a minor problem because of their informative interest.

This corpus is composed of several lists, arranged internally in chronological order. A first list, in Arabic numerals, shows the pieces that have been removed from the mummies with which they were associated, and which are mostly housed in museum institutions. A second list, arranged in Latin letters, presents the doubtful examples. Thirdly, the items ordered by Roman numerals are those discovered by the x-raying or scanning of mummies. Finally, a list of the pieces currently on display in two display cases in Room 22 at the Egyptian Museum in Cairo has been included, ordered according to their corresponding SR numbers. At the end is an index of inventory numbers with the identification given in the corpus.

In the file of each of the pieces, the ‘Inventory number’ states, if known or published, the registration number(s) that the piece has at the museum where it is kept. The ‘Other numbers’ section includes other numbers of the embalming plates that are relevant to their identification or that of their owner. The most important is the ‘A-List’ that G. Daressy prepared for the objects and individuals buried at Bab el-Gasus.

‘Owner’ only states the name, without mentioning his/her parentage or titles. The names of kings and royal personae have been recorded in transcription and those of private persons in transliteration. ‘Material’ indicates the medium in which the piece was made. ‘Main motif’ presents, if known, the most relevant logoiconical content of the piece (*wedjat*-eye, Sons of Horus, text(s), etc.). ‘Decoration’ records the materials and techniques used to create the appearance, texts, and images of the piece. ‘Observations’ include, if appropriate, some particular or interesting details. The ‘References’ are limited to the minimum and most relevant.

This work has no other aim than to be a simple preliminary corpus that can serve as a basis for further studies of this kind of artefacts. It is an open list that can be expanded, enriched, and corrected in the future with access to sources that have not yet consulted, the publication of new studies, museum collections and new findings⁵.

A. Embalming plates removed from mummies

[1]

Inventory number: London, BM EA 58942.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: –

Date: New Kingdom.

Owner: –

Material(s): silver.

⁴ Bothmer 1974: 121-122. Among the pieces currently on view are not anepigraphic and undecorated examples.

⁵ The genesis of this corpus of artefacts is in the study of a plate of this kind that was kindly entrusted by the director of the *Proyecto Djehuty*, José M. Galán Allué (CSIC), to Jesús Herrérin López (Dpto. de Biología, UAM) and myself. I would like to thank both for their generosity and observations, which I also extend to Salima Ikram (AUC) for her help in the initial stages of this research.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: –

References: <https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/Y_EA58942>.

[2]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Western Thebes, Valley of the Kings, KV 46.

Date: late Eighteenth Dynasty, reign of Amenhotep III.

Owner: Yuia.

Material(s): gold.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: fusiform.

References: Smith apud Quibell 1908: 68.

[3]

Inventory number: Cairo, JE 61835; M 311.

Other numbers: Carter 256d.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Valley of the Kings, KV 62.

Date: late Eighteenth Dynasty, reign of Tutankhamun.

Owner: Tutankhamun.

Material(s): gold.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: oval shape.

References: Reeves 1990: 112-113.

[4]

Inventory number: Cairo, JE 36355.

Other numbers: A.20.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: Twenty-first – Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: T3w-ḥnwt.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1903: 155; Aston 2009: 167.

[5]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.23.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: Twenty-first – Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: Nsj-p3-k3=f.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling.

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1903: 152; Janot 2000: 154; Aston 2009: 167.

[6]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.45.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: Twenty-first – Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: $\overline{D}d$ -Mwt-jw=s- \overline{nh} .

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: ?

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 25; Aston 2009: 172.

[7]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.54.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: Twenty-first – Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: –

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: painting and silver plated.

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 26; Aston 2009: 173.

[8]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.74.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: Twenty-first – Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: –

Material(s): silver.

Main motif: –

Decoration: gilding.

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 28; Aston 2009: 176.

[9]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.77.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: Twenty-first – Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: Nsjt-nb-tʃwj.
Material(s): white wax.
Main motif: –
Decoration: –
Observations: –
References: Aston 2009: 176.

[10]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?
Other numbers: A.102.
Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.
Date: Twenty-first – Twenty-second Dynasty.
Owner: Hʃ=s.
Material(s): red wax.
Main motif: –
Decoration: –
Observations: –
References: Daressy 1908: 30; Aston 2009: 181.

[11]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?
Other numbers: A.141.
Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.
Date: Twenty-first – Twenty-second Dynasty.
Owner: Dd-Hnsw-jw=f-ḥ.
Material(s): wood.
Main motif: wedjat-eye.
Decoration: gilding.
Observations: –
References: Daressy 1908: 36; Aston 2009: 191.

[12]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?
Other numbers: A.150.
Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.
Date: Twenty-first – Twenty-second Dynasty.
Owner: Dd-Mwt-jw=s-ḥ.
Material(s): lead.
Main motif: wedjat-eye.
Decoration: incision.
Observations: –
References: Daressy 1908: 37; Aston 2009: 194.

[13]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?
Other numbers: A.18.
Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: T3-šjt.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 23; Aston 2009: 167.

[14]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.39.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Jmn-ḥtp(.w).

Material(s): bronze.

Main motif: *wedjat-eye*.

Decoration: painting, gilding and silver plated.

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 25; Aston 2009: 170.

[15]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.106.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Ḥnsw-m-ḥb.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: shape of the leaf of a water lily.

References: Daressy 1908: 30; Aston 2009: 182.

[16]

Inventory number: London, BM EA 8409.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: –

Date: Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: –

Material(s): tin.

Main motif: *wedjat-eye*.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: –

References: Taylor 2011: 42;

https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/Y_EA8409.

[17]

Inventory number: London, BM EA 8410.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: –

Date: Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: –

Material(s): tin.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations:

References: <https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/Y_EA8410>.

[18]

Inventory number: London, BM EA 15572.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: –

Date: Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: –

Material(s): red wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling.

Observations: curved.

References: Taylor 2010: 37, fig. 26;

<https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/Y_EA15572>.

[19]

Inventory number: New York, MMA 25.3.164.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, MMA 60.

Date: Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: G3wt-sšn.

Material(s): bronze.

Main motif: wedjat-eye on a reed mat.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: –

References: Winlock 1926: 23-24 and 25, fig. 28 (left); Aston 2009: 201.

[20]

Inventory number: New York, MMA 25.3.165.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, MMA 60.

Date: Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Tjy.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling.

Observations: –

References: Winlock 1926: 23-24 and 25, fig. 28 (right); Goff 1979: 147, n. 87; Aston 2009: 201.

[21]

Inventory number: New York, MMA 25.3.171k.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, MMA 60, chamber 4.

Date: Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Ḥnwt-ḥwj (C).

Material(s): iron.

Main motif: ?

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: D'Auria et al. 1988: 163; Aston 2009: 200.

[22]

Inventory number: New York, MMA 25.3.173f.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, MMA 60, chamber 1.

Date: Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Nst-ḥst.

Material(s): iron.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: triangular shape with rounded corners.

References: Goff 1979: 111; Aston 2009: 201.

[23]

Inventory number: Paris, Louvre N 4369.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: –

Date: Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: –

Material(s): copper.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision, black painting, gilding.

Observations: shape of wedjat-eye in the upper part.

References:

http://cartelfr.louvre.fr/cartelfr/visite?srv=car_not_frame&idNotice=3983&langue=fr.

[24]

Inventory number: Cairo, JE 41586.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, TT 320.

Date: early Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Henuttawy.

Material(s): gold.

Main motif: *wedjat*-eye on divine standard, standing mummiform Sons of Horus, name of the owner, framework.

Decoration: relief, incision.

Observations: –

References: Smith 1912: 102, pl. lxxvi, fig. 2.

[25]

Inventory number: Cairo, JE 85821.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Tanis, precinct of Amun, Royal Tomb III.

Date: early Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Psusennes I.

Material(s): gold.

Main motif: *wedjat*-eye, standing Sons of Horus, name of the owner, framework.

Decoration: relief, incision.

Observations: –

References: Montet 1951: 148 (no. 527), pl. cxii; Aston 2009: 45.

[26]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.64.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: early Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Hnwt-ḥwj.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 27; Aston 2009: 174.

[27]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.96.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: early Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Ns-ḥ-wḏt-ḥ(t).

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 30; Aston 2009: 180.

[28]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.109.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: early Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Dd-M3'(t)-jw=s-ḥ.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 31; Aston 2009: 183.

[29]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.144.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: early Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: T3-jrt-R'.

Material(s): white wax (?).

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: ?

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 37; Aston 2009: 192.

[30]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.108.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: early-mid Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: ḥ=f-n-Ḥnsw.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 31; Aston 2009: 183.

[31]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.33.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first – early Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: ḥ=f-n-Ḥnsw.

Material(s): copper.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: shape of wedjat-eye.

References: Daressy 1908: 24; Aston 2009: 169.

[32]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.12.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Ns-p³-nb-jm³h.

Material(s): red wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: ?

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 22; Aston 2009: 166.

[33]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.13.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Mwt-p³-jr-shrw.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 22; Aston 2009: 166.

[34]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.58.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: }st-m-}h-bjt.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling.

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 26; Aston 2009: 174.

[35]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.81.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Jmn-njwt-nht.

Material(s): red wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 28; Aston 2009: 177.

[36]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.82.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Ḥnsw-ms(.w).

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: ?

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 29; Aston 2009: 177.

[37]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.83.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Dd-Ḥnsw-jw=s-ḥ.

Material(s): red wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: very large.

References: Daressy 1908: 29; Aston 2009: 178.

[38]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.85.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: P3-sb3-ḥ'-n-njw.t.

Material(s): bronze.

Main motif: –

Decoration: gilding.

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 29; Aston 2009: 178.

[39]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.98.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Ns-p3-Nfr-ḥr.

Material(s): red wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: black painting and silver plated on the modelled eye.

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 30; Aston 2009: 180.

[40]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.105.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Wsr-ḥꜣt-ms(.w).

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: ?

Observations: shape of wedjat-eye.

References: Daressy 1908: 30; Aston 2009: 182.

[41]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.113.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Nsj-Jmn-(m-)jpt.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 31; Aston 2009: 184.

[42]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.114.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Pꜣ-dj-Jmn.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: ?

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 31; Aston 2009: 184.

[43]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.119.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: T(ꜣ)-n(j)t-Jpt.

Material(s): red wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: ?

Observations: very thin.

References: Daressy 1908: 32; Aston 2009: 185.

[44]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.120.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Ḥnsw-m-rnp.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: ?

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 32; Aston 2009: 186.

[45]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.127.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: T3-ꜣ(t)-Jmn.

Material(s): papyrus.

Main motif: name of the owner.

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 34; Aston 2009: 187-188.

[46]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.135.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Mn-ḥpr-R'.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling.

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 36; Aston 2009: 189.

[47]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.26.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-late Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Nsj-pꜣwtj-ḫwj.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 23; Aston 2009: 168.

[48]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.30.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-late Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Šd-sw-Jmn.

Material(s): red wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 23; Aston 2009: 168.

[49]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.32.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-late Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: T3-ḥwtj.

Material(s): copper.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: ?

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 24; Aston 2009: 168.

[50]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.38.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-late Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: 'nh=s-n-Mwt.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 24.

[51]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.66.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-late Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: 3sty.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 28; Aston 2009: 175.

[52]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.71.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-late Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Mrt-Jmn.

Material(s): wood.

Main motif: –

Decoration: gilding.

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 28; Aston 2009: 176.

[53]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.126.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-late Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: 3st-m-(3h-)bjt.

Material(s): lead.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 33; Aston 2009: 187.

[54]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.134.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-Twenty-first – early Twenty-Second Dynasty.

Owner: Šd-Hrw.

Material(s): wood.

Main motif: ?

Decoration: gilding.

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 35; Aston 2009: 189.

[55]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.17.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: late Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: T(3)-n(j)t-p(3)-hrw-nfr.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: ?

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 23; Aston 2009: 166.

[56]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.43.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: late Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Ns-p³-q³-šwtj.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 25; Aston 2009: 172.

[57]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.125.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: late Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Ḥpw.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling.

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 33; Aston 2009: 187.

[58]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.133.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: late Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Ḥrw-wbn(.w).

Material(s): copper and gold.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 35.

[59]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.59.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: late Twenty-first – early Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: S³t-Ḥnsw.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 27; Aston 2009: 174.

[60]

Inventory number: Cairo, JE 35406.

Other numbers: A.91.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: late Twenty-first – early Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: T3-djt-Mwt.

Material(s): red wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelled black wax (eye), silver-plated (eyeball).

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1902: 154; 1908: 29.

[61]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.148.

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: late Twenty-first – early Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: Ns-Jmn.

Material(s): copper and gold.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: ?

Observations: –

References: Daressy 1908: 37; Aston 2009: 193.

[62]

Inventory number: –

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Tell el-Balamun, temple precinct, tomb 1.

Date: Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: Jkn.

Material(s): bronze.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Aston 2009: 72.

[63]

Inventory number: –

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Western Thebes, Dra Abu el-Naga.

Date: Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: –

Material(s): copper and gold.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: –

References: Carter 1916: 153; Aston 2009: 160.

[64]

Inventory number: Cairo, CG 61095 (mummy).

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, TT 320.

Date: early Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: Neskonsu A.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: –

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: Smith 1912: 108; Aston 2009: 228.

[65]

Inventory number: Cairo, CG 61097 (mummy).

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, TT 320.

Date: early Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: Djedptahiufankh A.

Material(s): bronze.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: –

References: Smith 1912: 112, pl. xciii.

[66]

Inventory number: Cairo, JE 87100.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Tanis, precinct of Amun, Royal Tomb III.

Date: early Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: Hornakht C.

Material(s): gold.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: relief.

Observations: –

References: Montet 1947: 69, pl. lxi; Aston 2009: 57.

[67]

Inventory number: SMDAN 4843*.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Western Thebes, Dra Abu el-Naga, Spanish Mission's concession.

Date: early-mid Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: –

Material(s): tin and lead.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: framework of 'metopes'

References: Herrerín López and Borrego Gallardo in press.

[68]

Inventory number: London, UC 52459.

Other numbers: –

Provenance:

Date: Late Period.

Owner: –

Material(s): silver (?).

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: partly broken.

References: Petrie 1914: 33, pl. xxiv (139n).

[69]

Inventory number: London, UC 52460.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: –

Date: Late Period.

Owner: –

Material(s): lead.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: partly broken.

References: Petrie 1914: 33, pl. xlvii (139n2)

[70]

Inventory number: London, UC 52461.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: –

Date: Late Period.

Owner: –

Material(s): tin and lead.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: shape of wedjat-eye; partly broken.

References: Petrie 1914: 33, pl. xlvii (139n8).

[71]

Inventory number: London, UC 52462.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: –

Date: Late Period.

Owner: –

Material(s): copper.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: relief.

Observations: partly broken.

References: Petrie 1914: 33, pl. xlvii (139n4).

[72]

Inventory number: London, UC 52463.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: –

Date: Late Period.

Owner: –

Material(s): bronze.

Main motif: *wedjat*-eye.

Decoration: relief; incrustation of white limestone and coloured glass.

Observations: –

References: <<http://petrieCAT.museums.ucl.ac.uk/search.aspx>>.

[73]

Inventory number: Paris, Louvre N 4341b

Other numbers: –

Provenance: –

Date: Late Period.

Owner: –

Material(s): tin (?).

Main motif: *wedjat*-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: shape of *wedjat*-eye in the upper part.

References: Étienne 2009: 130 (no. 94).

[74]

Inventory number: Cairo, JE 34516.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Saqqara, area of the pyramid of Wenis.

Date: Twenty-sixth Dynasty.

Owner: T3-n(j)-n(3)-hbw.

Material(s): silver.

Main motif: *wedjat*-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: –

References: Barsanti 1900: 271; Maspero 1902: 2.

[75]

Inventory number: Cairo, M 6341.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Tell Atrib.

Date: Twenty-sixth Dynasty, reign of Psamtik II.

Owner: Takhuit.

Material(s): gold.

Main motif: ?

Decoration: ?

Observations: –

References: Anonymous 1956: 170.

[76]

Inventory number: Boston, MFA 20.261.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Nuri, pyramid 22.

Date: Napatan Period.

Owner: Malenra (?).

Material(s): gold.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: –

References: <<https://collections.mfa.org/objects/142228>>.

[77]

Inventory number: Boston, MFA 72.4465.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: –

Date: Third Intermediate Period / Late Period.

Owner: –

Material(s): tin and lead.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: partly broken.

References: D'Auria et al. 1988: 222 (no. 173).

[78]

Inventory number: Leiden, RMO BA 221.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: –

Date: ?

Owner: –

Material(s): tin (?) / lead (?).

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: partly broken.

References: <https://www.rmo.nl/en/collection/search-collection/collection-piece/?object=15268>.

B. Doubtful examples

[A]

Inventory number: Cairo, ?

Other numbers: A.71 [bis].

Provenance: Western Thebes, Deir el-Bahari, Bab el-Gasus.

Date: mid-late Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Mrt-Jmn (?).

Material(s): bronze.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: gilding and silver plated.

Observations: shape of wedjat-eye.

References: Daressy 1908: 28.

C. Plaques documented through x-rays or scanning

[i]

Inventory number of the mummy: Musée des Beaux-Arts et d'Archéologie, Besançon, A.781.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Western Thebes (?).

Date: Twenty-first Dynasty.

Owner: Sr-Jmn.

Material(s): metal.

Main motif: wedjat-eye (?).

Decoration: incised (?).

Observations: –

References: Mérigeaud 2010: 199, fig. 5.

[ii]

Inventory number of the mummy: London, BM EA 30720.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Western Thebes.

Date: Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: Ns-pr-n(j)-Nbw.

Material(s): metal.

Main motif: ?

Decoration: –

Observations:

References: Taylor 2011: 7, 33, 34 and 42.

[iii]

Inventory number of the mummy: Hancock Museum, Newcastle upon Tyne, Aregypt605.

Other numbers:

Provenance: Western Thebes.

Date: Twenty-second Dynasty.

Owner: B3kt-n-Hrw-nht(.w).

Material(s): ?

Main motif: ?

Decoration: –

Observations: possibly displaced from its original position.

References: Watson and Myers 1993: 180, 181 and 183, fig. 1; Janot 2000: 151.

[iv]

Inventory number of the mummy: Manchester Museum, Manchester, 5053.a.

Other numbers: –

Provenance: Western Thebes, Dra Abu el-Naga.

Date: Twenty-fifth Dynasty.

Owner: Pr-n-B3st.

Material(s): metal (?).

Main motif: ?

Decoration: –

Observations: –

References: <<https://egyptmanchester.wordpress.com/2014/05/22/new-light-under-old-wrappings-ii-the-temple-singer-perenbast>>.

D. Plaques with Cairo Museum SR number

In the following list, the name of the owner, the provenance and the date are not recorded. It must be noted that it is highly probable that some plates from the mummies of the priests and priestesses buried in Bab el-Gasus (and classified under a number of the ‘list A’ de G. Daressy)⁶, maybe with a JE and TR numbers, are now on view among those located in two vitrines of the room 22 in the upper floor of the Egyptian Museum of Cairo.

SR 8715

Other numbers: TR 13-11-24-33

Material(s): red wax.

Main motif: *wedjat*-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: curved.

SR 8716

Other numbers: –

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: *wedjat*-eye.

Decoration: modelling, black painting.

Observations: curved, irregular shape.

SR 8717

Other numbers: –

Material(s): wood (?).

Main motif: *wedjat*-eye.

Decoration: gilding, incision.

Observations: –

SR 8718

Other numbers: TR 13-11-24-33.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: *wedjat*-eye.

Decoration: modelling, incision (eyebrow).

Observations: very large, curved.

SR 8719

Other numbers: –

Material(s): ?

Main motif: ?

Decoration: ?

Observations: retired from the exposition.

⁶ All the plaques on view in room 22 present the *wedjat*-eye. They are made in several materials, excluding gold and silver as main material. Thus, examples without decoration, such as several found in Bab el-Gasus, are not currently on view.

SR 8720

Other numbers: –

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: –

SR 8721

Other numbers: TR 13-11-24-11.

Material(s): wood (?).

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision, black painting (pupil, eye, eyebrow), silver-plated (eyeball).

Observations: –

SR 8722

Other numbers: –

Material(s): copper / bronze (?).

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: gilding, incision.

Observations: shape of wedjat-eye, openwork (lower part).

SR 8723

Other numbers: –

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision (?).

Observations: partly broken.

SR 8724

Other numbers: –

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling.

Observations: shape of wedjat-eye, crude execution.

SR 8725

Other numbers: JE 6267.

Material(s): lead (?).

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: –

SR 8726

Other numbers: TR 13-11-24-20.

Material(s): wood.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: gilding, relief.

Observations: –

SR 8727

Other numbers: –

Material(s): copper (?).

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: shape of wedjat-eye (upper part), partly broken.

SR 8728

Other numbers: TR 13-11-24-29.

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling.

Observations: –

SR 8729

Other numbers: –

Material(s): red wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: curved.

SR 8730

Other numbers: TR 13-11-24-28.

Material(s): copper (?).

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: gilding, incision.

Observations: large.

SR 8731

Other numbers: TR 13-11-24-26.

Material(s): copper / bronze (?).

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: gilding, incision.

Observations: –

SR 8732

Other numbers: TR 13-8-24-38.

Material(s): copper / bronze (?).

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision, silver plated.

Observations: (JE) 29720; curved.

SR 8733

Other numbers: –

Material(s): red wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: curved.

SR 8734

Other numbers: TR 13-11-24-34.

Material(s): tin.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: shape of wedjat-eye (upper part), rather long, partly broken.

SR 8735

Other numbers: TR 13-11-24-27.

Material(s): tin.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: partly broken.

SR 8736

Other numbers: –

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling.

Observations: large, partly broken.

SR 8737

Other numbers: –

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision, black painting.

Observations: broken.

SR 8738

Other numbers: –

Material(s): red wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling.

Observations: large.

SR 8758

Other numbers: –

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: curved, upper part partly broken.

SR 8759

Other numbers: –

Material(s): wood.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision, gilding.

Observations: shape of wedjat-eye.

SR 8760

Other numbers: –

Material(s): wood.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: gilding, incision, black painting (pupil, eye, eyebrow), silver-plated (eyeball).

Observations: shape of wedjat-eye in the upper part

SR 8761

Other numbers: –

Material(s): wood.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling / relief, gilding.

Observations: –

SR 8762

Other numbers: –

Material(s): copper (?).

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: curved.

SR 8763

Other numbers: –

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling, black painting (pupil, eye, eyebrow), silver-plated (eyeball).

Observations: curved.

SR 8764

Other numbers: –

Material(s): bronze (?).

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: shape of wedjat-eye (openwork).

SR 8765

Other numbers: –

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling, black painting, silver-plated (eyeball).

Observations: curved.

SR 8766

Other numbers: –

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: curved.

SR 8767

Other numbers: –

Material(s): red wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling.

Observations: curved.

SR 8768

Other numbers: –

Material(s): red wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling.

Observations: –

SR 8769

Other numbers: –

Material(s): metal.

Main motif: ?

Decoration: ?

Observations: small.

SR 8770

Other numbers: –

Material(s): white wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: incision.

Observations: curved.

SR 8771

Other numbers: –

Material(s): red wax.

Main motif: wedjat-eye.

Decoration: modelling.

Observations: curved.

Concordance of inventory numbers and entries of the corpus

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